

NOTES

pound(II) has also been prepared by us via two other routes : (Method 2) via reaction of dicyandiamide and *p*-toluenesulphonylchloride in aqueous medium and (Method 3) via reaction of dicyandiamide and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid in aqueous medium. That this compound is a salt of dicyandiamidine is shown by the following evidence : (1) The analytical results are those demanded by such a formulation (cf. Table 1). (2) The infra-red spectra of all the three preparations by the three methods are superimposable and do not betray any nitrile (C≡N) band^a around 2174 cm⁻¹ but do show a strong carbonyl (C=O) stretch^a around 1740 cm⁻¹ (cf. C=O stretch of dicyandiamidine sulphate at 1740 cm⁻¹). (3) All these three compounds react immediately with copper(II) and nickel(II) in alkaline medium to provide violet and orange-coloured compounds respectively. These compounds have superimposable infra red spectra with the corresponding copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes obtained from reaction with dicyandiamidine sulphate⁴ in alkaline medium.

(a) Found for the violet *bis*(dicyandiamidine) copper(II) obtained via reaction of CuCl₂, dicyandiamidine *p*-toluenesulphonate in presence of NaOH : Cu, 23.6% ; N, 20.9%.

(b) Found for the similar violet compound obtained from CuCl₂, dicyandiamidine sulphate and NaOH : Cu, 23.7% ; N, 20.9%.

(c) Required for *bis*(dicyandiamidine) copper(II), [Cu(C₂N₄OH₂)₂] : Cu, 23.9% ; N, 21.1%

All these copper(II) complexes exhibit C=O stretch around 1740 cm⁻¹ but no nitrile band at 2174 cm⁻¹.

Dicyandiamide(III) is well known to add a molecule of H₂O to its nitrile group in presence of aqueous acids (say, H₂SO₄) giving appropriate salt of dicyandiamidine(IV).

In the Methods (1-3) cited above the media are sufficiently acid to produce *p*-toluenesulphonate salt of dicyandiamidine rather than a *p*-toluenesulphonate substituted dicyandiamide

An authentic sample of *p*-toluenesulphonyl dicyandiamide was finally obtained by reacting dicyandiamide with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride in alkaline (sodium hydroxide) water-acetone medium and operating at 18-20°. Under these reaction conditions the nitrile group was not sensitive to hydrolysis. Instead, the dicyandiamide-NH₂ reacted with the -SO₂Cl group liberating HCl which was immediately removed by the excess alkali. At the end, the reaction medium was neutralised with acetic acid and the *p*-toluenesulphonyldicyandiamide crystallised. The elemental analyses of the product are quite satisfactory (Table 1) The infrared spectrum of the compound shows the absence of the carbonyl stretch around 1740 cm⁻¹ but does exhibit a sharp, strong nitrile (C≡N) band around 2174 cm⁻¹. Unlike dicyandiamidine this compound fails to give an immediate reaction with copper(II) or nickel(II) salts in presence of alkali.

Experimental

*Dicyandiamidine p-toluenesulphonate : Method 1 (Sen and Gupta's alleged synthesis)*²

p-Toluenesulphonyl chloride (10.5 g), dicyandiamide (4.2 g), sodium acetate (10.2 g) and water (25 ml) were refluxed for 2 hrs. *p*-Toluenesulphonyl chloride formed a separate layer (on melting) in the beginning, which gradually disappeared with the completion of the reaction. The resulting solution was allowed to stand overnight and the crystals were filtered. These were purified from aqueous ethanol.

Method 2 : p-Toluenesulphonylchloride (10.5 g) and dicyandiamide (4.2 g) in water (60 ml) were refluxed on a steam bath until the mixture formed a homogenous solution (2 hr). It was then worked up as in Method 1.

Method 3 : p-Toluenesulphonic acid (8.6 g) and were refluxed in water (60 ml). It was then worked up as in Method 1.

p-Toluenesulphonyldicyandiamide : Dicyandiamide

^a This method is parallel to those described by P. P. Winnek and coworkers⁵ for a large number of substituted dicyandiamides.

TABLE-1 CHARACTERISATION DATA OF DICYANDIAMIDINE *p*-TOLUENESULPHONATE (C₉H₁₄N₄O₆S) AND *p*-TOLUENESULPHONYLDICYANDIAMIDE (C₉H₁₀N₄O₅S)

Compound	M.P. (°C)	Carbon (%)	Hydrogen (%)	Nitrogen (%)	Sulphur (%)
C ₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₆ S					
Method-1**	234.5	—	—	20.0(20.4)*	11.9(11.7)
Method-2	235.0	—	—	20.4(20.4)	11.5(11.7)
Method-3	235.0	40.0(39.4)	5.4(5.1)	20.3(20.4)	11.8(11.7)
C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₅ S	191.0	45.1(45.4)	4.5(4.2)	23.7(23.5)	13.8(13.5)

*Calculated values are in parentheses.

**Sen and Gupta's analyses are : M.P. (235°) ; % Nitrogen 23.4(23.5)

(8.4 g) was suspended in acetone (120 ml) and sodium hydroxide (10 g in 20 ml water) was added. The mixture was cooled to 18° and *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (19.1 g) was added gradually with stirring, while the temperature was maintained at 18°. After the reaction mixture was stirred for four hours it was allowed to stand overnight. The solution was diluted with water (100 ml) and neutralised with acetic acid. *p*-Toluenesulphonyldicyandiamide separated as white crystals. These were recrystallised from methanol and dried in air.

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Stereochemical Studies on Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Complexes with *p*-Dimethyl Amino-9-anthracyl Glyoxal Anil

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NEW complexes of Co(II) and Ni(II) with *p*-dimethyl amino 9-anthracyl glyoxalanil (DIMAGA) of the type [M(C₂₄H₂₀N₂O)₂(Cl)₂] [where M=Co(II), Ni(II)] have been prepared and characterised on the basis of various physicochemical studies. Magnetic

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moment and electronic-spectral studies of the complexes reveal the octahedral stereochemistry. The i. r. data indicate (M-O), (M-N) and (M-Cl) stretching frequencies in the range 575-560, 520-500 and 340-320 cm⁻¹ respectively.

Recently, in connection with our interest in the stereochemical studies on transition metal complexes with DIMAGA^{1,2}, we here report the synthesis of Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes with DIMAGA and their characterization by chemical-analysis, molecular conductance, magnetic moment (at 305°K using Guoy's method), electronic spectra (indioxane) and infra-red studies.

Preparation and Isolation of Complexes : Dichlorobis-(DIMAGA) Cobalt(II)/Nickel(II) : The acetonic solution of NiCl₂.6H₂O or CoCl₂.6H₂O (2.37 g., 10 m. mole) was mixed with (7.04 g., 20 m. mole) of the ligand DIMAGA in the same solvent and dark-grey (Co-complex) and buff-green (Ni-complex) precipitates obtained were digested, cooled, filtered and washed with small amounts of ethanol, acetonitrile and acetone. The products were dried at 80°-90° for about 30 minutes. The molar conductance of the complexes in 10⁻³ M DMF solution [$\lambda_m = 20.89$ and 11.5 mhos for Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes respectively] suggest their non-electrolytic nature.

Chemicals of 'AnalaR' grade are used throughout. Elemental analysis was made for both the complexes and satisfactory agreement was obtained between found and calculated values revealing metal to ligand stoichiometric ratio as 1 : 2. The electronic spectra were recorded in dioxane using Hilger UviA-peck spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurements and i. r. spectra of the complexes were undertaken as described earlier.¹

The observed magnetic moment in Co(II) complex (4.60 B. M.) is slightly lower to the spin only value, which indicates low spin octahedral stereochemistry with incomplete quenching of the orbital contribution to the magnetic moment.³ The observed magnetic moment in Ni(II) complex (2.98 B.M.) also suggests octahedral symmetry. The slight increase in magnetic moment value from that of the spin only value may be due to some sort of mixing of upper states via spin orbit coupling.⁴